

Impact of Western Fashion over Traditional Fashion in Pakistan

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Abstract:

Students' lives are profoundly influenced by Western fashion, both positively and negatively. There is a lack of skepticism regarding the influence of culture on the education and lifestyle of young people. The purpose of this study was to determine the effects of Western culture on the way of life of college students on various university campuses. The purpose of this extensive study is to educate young people about the negative effects of cultural imperialism on their university experience. Both male and female university students made up the sample population for this study. The data was collected using a Likert scale questionnaire. Research shows that Western culture has had a significant influence on university students' social and lifestyle ideals. Every aspect of university life, from social differences to cultural preferences, has been strongly influenced by Western culture. According to the students' own words, Western culture has had an effect on even the most mundane aspects of university life, such as the process of being rejected.

Keywords: Western fashion/culture, Traditional fashion/culture, Youth lifestyle, Mass media, Ethics & values.

Introduction

People's beliefs, symbols, values, and customs form the foundation of their culture. Traditional groupings and good social groups (nontraditional 'subcultures,' such as free-spirit culture and the Internet culture) have traditionally arisen in certain places under the word 'culture.' As a people's whole way of life, including their beliefs, customs, language, and traditions, may be defined as their culture. Western culture, on the other hand, is diametrically opposed. Both civilizations have a well-rounded way of life on display. However, the two modes of living are vastly different. Pakistan is a Muslim country, and its culture reflects a unique set of religious beliefs, ideals, and practices. Islam in Pakistan is a system of customs that govern the way Pakistanis live their cultural lives. Because of nationalization and westernization, the People have absorbed western culture (Featherstone, 1990).

Pakistani society is being 'Westernized' as a result of the cultural mix. Westernization is the mode of Modernization that lesser civilizations embrace. Behaving in a manner consistent with the upper and lower-middle classes Universities in Pakistan have also been affected by the modernization of Western culture (Inglehart & Baker, 2000).

Clothing, food, and other aspects of daily life change as society progresses. Societal trends are influenced by a variety of variables. In spite of the fact that there has been no significant cultural development, their religions, norms, and beliefs are markedly different (Buchanan, 2006).

Because we live in a materialistic environment, the attire in the West is more of a fusion of wanton kinds. The current fashion scene is influenced by the West. Their attire comprises jeans, t-shirts, skirts, trousers, shorts, and more. Even three-piece suits are considered formal attire. The clothing code is not dictated by a person's religious beliefs. Comfort and style are the defining characteristics of western wear. A woman wears just what she finds attractive, comfortable, and flattering. As a general rule, Europeans tend to follow the same path. Anywhere in the western world, the preference is for mix-matched dresses decorated with embellishments. Fashion in the West is a product of liberalism and an open mind (Buchanan, 2006).

The dress of the East, on the other hand, is rapidly evolving in terms of tradition and culture. The clothing code in the east is influenced by religious beliefs, cultural responsibilities, and customs. When it comes to eastern culture, wearing traditional and customary attire is regarded as an essential part of preserving what they believe in and passing this along to future generations. When all cultures are brought together, a new and contemporary design of clothing has emerged that has been popular in both the west and the east (Buchanan, 2006).

We all desire perfection in our appearances, and every female wants to stand out from the crowd. Fashion has always been an important part of women's life, regardless of the historical period in which they live. Well-dressed women are not only gorgeous, but they also radiate a radiance of beauty because, if a person's facial characteristics, form, skin tone, or height are lacking, fashionable clothing may mask these flaws (Berger, 2011).

Mass Media

Today's media is involved in everything, or it has devised ways to attack anything or play a role in the devastation of any sort. "Media in fashion" refers to the fact that today's world is dominated by the media; a few decades ago, fashion was less popular with the general public, but now it has established itself as a major industry and provides information about the most current trends in fashion via print, electronic, and digital media. An investigation on how many British women are fashion-obsessed discovered that a huge percentage of women chose restricted designs from media such as television shows, movies, magazines, and so on (McFatter, 2005).

Fashion shows centered on new outfit designs were formerly popular, but not anymore because of the popularity of television, which now has one or more TVs in every home, as well as cable or satellite connections or dishes (David, 2009). Fashion is a part of the culture, and it has the power to expand or contract that culture. The systems that allow people to expand or contract culture begin with media such as radio, television, fashion shows, the internet, social media platforms, newspapers, and billboards and banners, all of which influence how people dress (Barnes & Greenwood, 2006).

Since television is now a staple in nearly every home, children, adolescents, young adults, and adults all have easy access to it. This connection serves to illustrate their image as the people who perform on TV screens and encourages them to pursue their own unique personas. Today, everyone wants to create their personality because the media tells a story of a teacher and creates an impressive image of perfect identity (Hamely, 2001). Our way of life is being developed through the fashion industry's use of print and electronic media, which exhibit branded clothing, footwear, jewelry, and other accessories... When it comes to fashion, adolescent girls tend to focus on trimming their bodies and making their social status; they also accept different first-class outfits in order to appear stunning on the television screen (Brandon, 2011).

Effects on Pakistani Society

Religious motivation is a major factor in Pakistani society, which divides along religious lines. As far as Pakistani society is concerned, the Pakistani government has laid down an Islamic relevance indicator. Allowing for native needs and perceptions, society in Pakistan adopts Western influences and modernity (Rana & Chishti, 2017).

The world's fashion industry may be dominated by Western attire, but countries and states are nonetheless committed to maintaining ties with their traditional clothing. New fashion trends in their ethnic attire are always being introduced to them. Change throughout time is unavoidable in any society. Fashion trends are also influenced by the changing culture in the location where they are popular. After marriage in India, women were required to wear a Sari. As a result, ladies were able to stay at home while their husbands went out to work. Women are no longer confined to wearing a Sari since they contribute more to the family's income. As a result, culture has a significant impact on regional fashion. A society's fashion trends are only an imitation of its culture. Fashion evolves as the culture shifts! Fashion may also have a significant impact on a region's culture. However, the current era's dominance is the reverse (Rana & Chishti, 2017).

Societies are governed by cultural norms and values, which serve as a guide for how people interact with each other and their environment (Danforth, 2008). However, Hodgetts (2006) argued that culture is a set of learning materials that we use to interpret policies and construct social strategies. As a result of this increased understanding, many values, mindsets, and behavior incentives are being developed. Culture, according to (Shah & Amjad, 2011), may be viewed as a value of a connection that allows individuals to be themselves as time passes. Despite the fact that Pakistan is a multi-cultural nation that values its diverse populations, it's important to note that Pakistani culture encompasses all of these aspects in addition to the language and literature. It also incorporates the religious practices, the music and art forms, as well as the clothes and ornamentation used by the people of Pakistan. Pakistan's society has strong cultural ties to the

West because of the region's history of dependence on the West, and because of the vast minority groups who live and dress in Pakistan. Pakistani society is naturally diverse, but not massive (Paracha, 2015).

Ethics and Values of lifestyle

Because Pakistan is divided into four distinct cultural groups (Sindhi, Punjabi, Pakhtoon, and Baloch), there are wide disparities in everything from racial ideals to languages and lifestyles to even ethical principles. People in India's traditional beliefs lives, traditions and behaviors are on the verge of a major shift toward the west (Hakim & Aziz, 1998).

A lifestyle is a collection of possibilities and behaviors toward life that may be based on one's values and beliefs or on societal, cultural, or other unknown causes (Nahas, Barros & Francalacci, 2000). Cultural notions are also influenced by a wide range of personal living decisions (McGaughey, 2018). At several points throughout the process, culture can be activated (Ahmed, 2020). The cultural variables influence people's opinions and perceptions about Western civilization (Lake, Staiger, & Glowinski, 1999). The two-fold frame may slow down distinct aspects of the combination, even though country or cultural beginning is frequently employed as a change for a different set of followers traditionally governed by ethics (Sibani, 2018).

Mass Media influencing Western Fashion over Traditional Fashion

According to the media, we've seen a dramatic increase in our nation's Westernization. The media in Pakistan has a major influence on governance, legislative concerns, financial chores, education, and religion, which are all closely related. Wearing westernized clothing, translators are divided into many categories by T.V networks. Despite this, television shows are reimagining classic moments in new ways. In fact, even our television shows are now emphasizing western-style clothing and a more formal set design. List, magazine, board, etc. appear to show how westernization has spread throughout Pakistan. Stone Age's portfolio may be viewed here. Magazines and TV shows offer up a wide range of issues that aren't discussed when people discuss our way of life, our settlements, or our religious beliefs. Individuals in the new era are being treated with contempt by the media at the moment. We are being woven into the web of westernization as a result of the Western liberal principles that have been introduced to us (Gellani, 1981).

According to (Zeb, Rashid & Bilal, 2011), there was a time when people wanted to wear their traditional garments like the shalwar Kameez; nevertheless, it appears that people are still wearing salwar Kameez, but fashion has changed the appearance of the garment. New trends, new fashions, and new brands may be found on television, on the internet, in fashion shows, in magazines, and in other media outlets (Walsh, Mitchell, Thurau, 2001, p.73). As a result of this approach, the media hides the reality and creates an extra world that allows observers to see the true world. In Gerbner's opinion, media is the most widely seen channel, and if somebody is a dependable media viewer, they will be steered toward a world of misunderstanding by the media (Schiappa, 2008).

People who regularly watch fashion shows on television will undoubtedly notice an individual's odd sense of style; even if it is consistent with the clothing they are wearing. After that, he or she will believe that the media always provides accurate information; therefore any kind of clothing he or she wears is appropriate for television advertising, regardless of how far it reaches. Then he or she will create an alternate reality that will lead them astray. In other words, the function of a storyteller is played by the mass media, which tells a different tale to various audiences and whether or not the story is real (Facts, 2011).

According to Schiappa (2008, p. 13), viewers' hubris is somewhat affected by the use of more media than the performance. Observers' boldness about the marvelous world is changed by mass media's light habit of guiding the unfamiliar toward accepting and embracing the shift, rather than focusing on the specifics. Gerbner also claims that this theory creates effects on levels, which are known as first demand effects (learn specifics from media) and second demand effects (learn unsure response regarding conventional beliefs from media) (learn uncertain answer about usual beliefs from media) (Wikipedia, 2004).

Effects on Pakistani society by influencing Western Fashion over Traditional Fashion

The diversity of Pakistani society sets it apart from others and makes it unique. Although it has its roots in different civilizations, the Islamic set of ideals it reflects is its most important component. In the meantime, Pakistani society has been shaken by the increasing globalization of the previous century. Pakistani

youngsters are seen to be increasingly interested in Western culture in this photograph. Social and electronic media, as well as publications, have hastened the dispersal of Westernized culture. As part of one's general public, culture serves as the unseen link that binds people together. A network's writing style, language, religion, and method all reflect its way of life. Throughout the ages, Pakistan's culture has preserved long-standing pacts. In any event, as time has progressed, western culture has exacerbated Pakistan's administrative, economic, and social woes while crushing its culture and way of life to such an extent that even the advancing years have weakened the country's authority. Common and sub-common networks and (sub) cultures are not invalidated by this supposition as stated in (Qadeer, 2006).

To our young people, it's a badge of honor to be referred to as "modern" in the cause of freedom. They desired self-determination and autonomy as a result of their adherence to Western culture. Parents' crisscrosses and remainders irritate them to no end. A man is born free, thus he shouldn't be constrained by the constraints of inquiring and replying. He is solely responsible for his own success, thus his family should not be keeping tabs on him. Students are more preoccupied with maintaining a healthy weight and physical appearance than they are with doing well in school. Drugs and other wrongdoing are common pastimes for many youngsters. Mugging and other unlawful actions have grown so commonplace. As Muslims, we should respect and love our parents, but today's parents must endure their children's questioning, shattering, shouting, hateful language, disagreement, and not forget suicides, murders, and other such activities when parents disapprove of them. This is a sad commentary on the state of Muslim parenting today (Gellani, 1981).

Every aspect of everyday life has been influenced by Western culture, from food to the most basic human rights. Westernization was not only a step toward modernization, but it was also a move toward the public's acceptance of it. Morality and ethics play a crucial role in building a just society in Islam, and they are rooted in mutual respect for Muslims. In order to compete in the modern world, young people are naturally drawn to Western culture. Modernity is often associated with sophistication, and vice versa. All of us want to be labeled as the latest and greatest. There has been a long-standing tradition of looking to the west to find the cause of any problem. For the people of Pakistan, the only answer to our problems and difficulties is to submit to the authority of the West, the established nations in the world. In the eyes of our young people, these nations are forward-thinking and have devised solutions to all of the world's issues, so it makes sense to emulate them without questioning whether or not what they are doing is morally right, Islamic, or otherwise (Gellani, 1981).

Ethics and Values of lifestyle are influencing Western Fashion over Traditional Fashion

A major contrast between Islamic and Western society may be seen in their religious beliefs. Our younger generation is enjoying the Western way of life because of their open-mindedness, which contrasts with their faith. Morality and ethics play a critical role in the development of an Islamic community, which is based on mutual respect for Muslims (Sultana & Bukhari, 2020).

Pakistan's ethos and culture are essentially mixed, with each cultural group originating its originality from its appearance's conventional principles and practices, which ultimately creates it distinct from others (Giorgetti, Campbell, & Arslan, 2017). Many cultural gatherings in Pakistan have sociological capacities and values that are distinct from those of the rest of the country (Hussain, 2016). In the territory now known as Pakistan, a diverse range of cultures and peoples have shown their disapproval, with British influence being the most noticeable and still active one (Rana & Chishti, 2017). Pakistan's culture is extraordinarily diverse, with a plethora of cultural events showcasing the country's many sociological potential and ideals (Hussain, 2016). Values, ideals, and ethics are discriminated against in Pakistani culture since they are based on religion. A list of Islamic moral principles has been compiled by the Pakistani government. The culturally corrected copy has been westernized (Nauman, 2015).

The lifestyles of students at Pakistan's educational institutions, notably its universities, are likewise highly prized. There is a need to categorize the impacts of Western culture and lifestyles on the Pakistani university environment. While lifestyle can be seen in unique kinds that cannot be publicly assessed (Ahmed & Naz, 2020; Ashiq, Abbas & Obaid, 2020).

Conclusion

Students in Pakistan's universities will be the focus of the study, which aims to examine the interaction between western fashion and traditional Pakistani dress. It was shown that overall mindset has a significant impact on the interaction between western fashion and traditional style transformation. People's lives have been profoundly impacted by modernism and western fashion as a result of globalization, and this impact is more pronounced in metropolitan regions than in rural ones. Traditional Pakistani design is gradually being replaced by western fashion, and Western principles are increasingly being questioned in Pakistani culture. The disparity shows that there is a wide range of attitudes toward Western fashion among the general public. People may think that if they were accepted by their family and society, they would wear it. This is an acceptable state; however, it is observed that fewer ladies wear traditional clothing because of a lack of perspective and approbation. When comparing the two styles, traditional clothing made a huge difference. The remainder of the differences appears to be indistinguishable from one another. This indicates that the comparison's sub-sections will be organized in this way. Many individuals place great importance on their ethnicity, culture, and traditions and wear clothing that reflects these values even on a day-to-day basis. 95 percent of the ladies are clothed in traditional Pakistani attire, which proves this point. People's thoughts are shaped by their core beliefs (such as their ethnicity and values) as well as their unique personality quirks. A lot of individuals aren't ready to embrace the truth that every clothing purchase selection has an ethnicity and beliefs at its core. Muslim women are quite picky when it comes to their clothing choices. As a rule, the material should not be too thin, the garment should not be overly revealing, and it should be simple to wear. The way we dress naturally enhances our appearance. Wearing Western clothing is thought to make women feel more formal as if they're portraying a Western-styled image. However, it is a common belief that Pakistani youth's dress style is undergoing a major shift due to the incorporation of Western fashion, particularly that of the United States. An attempt was made in the current study to determine the level of journalistic understanding of the media's role in influencing Pakistani fashion trends. Fashion journalists are seen as tastemakers, and they inform the public of what they think the public should buy.

References

- Ahmed, S. (2020). Cross cultural aspect of teaching of English as an international language. *Competitive Education Research Journal (CERJ)*, 1(2), 50-61.
- Ashiq, U., Abbas, N., & Obaid, A. (2020). The prospects threats of substance use and role of social and economic factors among youth: The case of higher education institutions. *Competitive Social Science Research Journal*, 1(2), 10–18.
- Baran, S. J. (2014). Introduction to Mass Communication: Media Literacy and Culture.
- Barnes, L., & Lea-Greenwood, G. (2006). Fast fashioning the supply chain: shaping the research agenda. *Journal of Fashion Marketing and Management: An International Journal*.
- Berger, J. (2011). Arousal increases social transmission of information. *Psychological science*, 22(7), 891-893.
- Bernard, H.R. (1989). *Research Methods in Cultural Anthropology*. California: Sage Publications Inc.
- Brandon, M. (2011, October 2). Media influence teenagers. In Examiner.com. Retrieved June 23, 2012, from <http://www.examiner.com/article/how-the-media-influences-teenagers>
- Buchanan, K. (2006). Job performance and satisfaction. URL. Retrieved May, 8, 2014.
- Carrither, M. (1992). *Why humans have cultures: Explaining anthropology and social diversity*. Oxford University Press.
- Danforth, C. G. (2008). In *Transforming Culture, A Model for Faith and Film in Hollywood*. Eugene: Wipf & Stock.
- Danforth, D. N. (2008). *Danforth's obstetrics and gynecology*. Lippincott Williams & Wilkins.
- David, D. (2009, July 15). Role of television in fashion industry: positive & negative effects.
- Featherstone, M. (1990). Perspectives on consumer culture. *Sociology*, 24(1), 5-22.
- Giorgetti, F. M. (2017). C. Campbell C. A. Arslan, *Pedagogical historic a*, 53(1-2), 1.
- Hakim, A., & Aziz, A. (1998). Socio-cultural, religious, and political aspects of the status of women in Pakistan. *The Pakistan development review*, 727-746.
- Hamely, K. (2001). Media use in identity construction. Retrieved August, 30, 2010.

- Hodgetts, R.M (2006) International Management. 6th Edition, McGraw Hill, Irwin.
- Holdorf, R. (2005). The role of teen-oriented fashion magazine content on clothing purchase behaviors and attitudes of adolescents and teens. *Florida State University D-Scholarship Repository*.
- Inglehart, R., & Baker, W. E. (2000). Modernization, cultural change, and the persistence of traditional values. *American sociological review*, 19-51.
- Janssen, S. (2006). Fashion reporting in cross-national perspective 1955–2005. *Poetics*, 34(6), 383– 406.doi: 10.1016/j.poetic.2006.10.001
- Kang, H. & Chang, B. (2016). Examining culture’s impact on the learning behaviors of international students from Confucius culture studying in western online learning context. *Journal of International Students*, 6(3), 779- 797.
- Lake, A. J., Staiger, P. K., & Glowinski, H. (2000). Effect of Western culture on women's attitudes to eating and perceptions of body shape. *International Journal of Eating Disorders*, 27(1), 83-89.
- McGaughey, E. (2018). Will Robots Automate Your Job Away? Full Employment, Basic Income and Economic Democracy. *Industrial Law Journal*.
- McGaughey, M. (2018). The Relationship between Body Image and Lifestyle Choices in College Students. *International Social Science Review*, 94(2), 3.
- Meşeci Giorgetti, F., Campbell, C., & Arslan, A. (2017). Culture and education: Looking back to culture through education. *Pedagogical Historic a*, 53(1-2), 1-6.
- Nauman, S. (2015). Investing in education: Pakistan as a traditional society in a modern world. *Journal of Education and Educational Development*, 2(1).
- Paracha, N. F. (2015). Pakistan culture: Evolution, transformation & mutation. *Dawn*, April, 10.
- Qadeer, M. A. (2006). Pakistan Social Cultural Transformation in Muslim Nation. New York, USA: Routledge.
- Qureshi, A. M., Baber, S., & Abbas, F. (2021). Impact of western culture on university students ‘lifestyle. *psychology and education*, 58(1), 4677-4687.
- Rana, A. M. K., & Chishti, M. H. (2019). Historical Perspective of cultural diversity; an effect of cultural change on student’s performance at university level in Pakistan. *Pakistan Vision*, 20(1), 1.
- Rana, K.A. & Chishti, H.M. (2017). Historical Perspective of cultural diversity; an effect of cultural change on student’s performance at university level in Pakistan. *Pakistan Vision*, 20(1), 2-10.
- Riaz, S., & Arif, U. (2019). Influence of Foreign TV Programs on Fashion, Lifestyle and Language of Youth. *Journal of Media Studies*, 32(2).
- Schiappa, E. (2008). *Beyond representational correctness: Rethinking criticism of popular media*. Sunny Press.
- Shah, S. A & Amjad, S. (2011). Cultural Diversity in Pakistan: National vs Provincial. *Mediterranean. Journal of Social Sciences (MJSS)*. 2, 331-344.
- Sheldon, K. M., Elliot, A. J., Ryan, R. M., Chirkov, V., Kim, Y., Wu, C., ... & Sun, Z. (2004). Self-concordance and subjective well-being in four cultures. *Journal of cross-cultural psychology*, 35(2), 209-223.
- Sibani, C. M. (2018). Impact of western culture on traditional African society: Problems and prospects. *Journal of Religion and Human Relations*, 10(1), 56-72.
- Sultana, M., & Bukhari, S. A. G. (2020). Challenges of Westernized Culture to Pakistani Society and Its Solution in the Light of Islamic Teachings. *Al-Azhār*, 6(1).
- Sultana, S. (2002). Critical analysis of fashion pages of leading English and Urdu dailies of Pakistan. (Unpublished Thesis). University of the Punjab, Lahore., Pakistan.
- Sun, T., Horn, M., & Merritt, D. (2004). Values and lifestyles of individualists and collectivists: a study on Chinese, Japanese, British and US consumers. *Journal of consumer marketing*.
- Walsh, G., MITCHELL, V. W., & Hennig-Thurau, T. H. O. R. S. T. E. N. (2001). German consumer decision-making styles. *Journal of Consumer Affairs*, 35(1), 73-95.
- Wesley, S., LeHew, M., & Woodside, A. G. (2006). Consumer decision-making styles and mall shopping behavior: Building theory using exploratory data analysis and the comparative method. *Journal of Business Research*, 59(5), 535-548.
- Wilkie, William L. (1994), *Consumer Behavior* (Third Edition), New York: John Wile & Sons, Inc.
- World Values Survey. The University of Michigan: Institute For Social Research; 2000–2001.

- Yau, O. H., & You, H. (1994). *Consumer behaviour in China: Customer satisfaction and cultural values*. Taylor & Francis.
- Zeb, H., Rashid, K., & Javeed, M. B. (2011). Influence of brands on female consumer's buying behavior in Pakistan. *International Journal of Trade, Economics and Finance*, 2(3), 225.